

Variation in appressoria and infection process of *Sclerotium oryzae*, which causes stem rot of rice

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Fifteen isolates of pathogen *S. oryzae* were collected from around India and studied to determine the variation in

appressoria produced. We also investigated the pathogen's mode of penetration, invasion, and establishment on rice.

Healthy pieces of stems of susceptible cultivar, TN1, were surface-sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride, washed with sterile distilled water three times, and inoculated with a sclerotium at the middle of the internode. Inoculated stem pieces were placed in a humid chamber and incubated at 28 ± 2 °C. Samples were taken at 4-h intervals from 24 to 72 h after incubation, killed, and fixed in FAA

solution made of 10 ml formaldehyde (37-40%), 50 ml ethyl alcohol (95%), 5 ml glacial acetic acid, and 35 ml distilled water.

We used the whole mount method to study specific infection stages. Peelings of inoculated portions were collected at intervals and passed through 50 and 30% alcohol followed by distilled water, stained in 0.1% aqueous aniline blue for 2 min, and dehydrated through 30, 50, 70, 90%, and absolute alcohol for 2 min at each grade. Peelings were then cleared in a xylene-alcohol series of 1:3, 1:1, 3:1, and pure xylene, and mounted in Canada balsam.

Sclerotia germinated 12-24 h after inoculation at the stem surface. Several branched, septate hyphae proliferated, possibly by utilizing nutrients in the sclerotium and/or at the surface of the stem, and formed a loosely interwoven mycelial mat (Fig. a). The mycelial mat, having direct contact with the host surface, started to swell and formed appressoria (Fig. b). The mycelium became closely septate and culminated into an appressorium when it came into

Development of *S. oryzae* on the stem of TN1 (600X).
a) Germinating sclerotia, b) growth of pathogen on host surface after 12-24 h, c) swelling of hyphae and initiation of appressoria formation, d) appressoria and subcuticular hyphae, e) development of infection peg from appressoria and penetration into epidermal cell, f) penetration by germ tube through cuticle, and g) hyphae ramifying in parenchymatous tissues of host.

Description of appressoria produced by *S. oryzae* isolates.

Isolate	Color of appressoria	Range in the dimensions of appressoria (mm) ^a		Lobes/appressorium (no.) ^a
		Length	Width	
Hyderabad (Andhra Pradesh)	Dark brown	13-29	7-23	8
Kapurthala (Punjab)	Dark brown	12-28	10-23	8
Titabar (Assam)	Brown	14-30	11-25	6
Kapurthala (Punjab)	Dark brown	12-28	10-23	8
Coimbatore (Tamil Nadu)	Brown	14-31	13-29	5
Madurai (Tamil Nadu)	Light brown	11-29	9-24	10
Kaul (Haryana)	Light brown	13-26	9-25	9
Lakhimpur (Uttar Pradesh) (UP)	Dark brown	15-33	12-29	8
Sitapur (UP)	Light brown	14-28	10-24	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	12-28	10-24	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	13-29	11-26	8
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	14-29	11-26	6
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	15-30	12-29	9
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	15-32	11-28	8
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	14-30	9-26	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	12-30	8-26	7

^aAv of 50 appressoria

contact with the host surface (Fig. c). All the isolates produced lobate, multicellular appressoria (Fig. d) that varied in color, size, and number of lobes/appressorium (Table 1).

The appressoria were observed to form infection pegs which penetrated directly through the cuticle into the epidermal cell and produced subepidermal mycelia (Fig. e). In some cases, an infection cushion did not form; hyphae penetrated directly through the host surface (Fig. f) and then ramified in parenchymatous tissues. As the hyphae thickened and branched, the host cell disintegrated and the host tissue became damaged extensively (Fig. g). ■

Managing ufra disease in deepwater rice (DWR) in Assam, India

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Ufra disease, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a major biotic constraint in DWR in Assam. We compared the effects of several management practices on disease severity under field conditions in a preidentified ufra-infected area. Experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seeds of popular (but highly ufra-susceptible) local DWR variety

Rangabao were sown at 15-d intervals on 20 Mar, 4 Apr, 19 Apr, and 4 May in 1990 and 1991 wet seasons. Disease severity was recorded as percentage of infected tillers/hill (Table 1).

In a separate experiment, we compared the effects of soaking seeds and/or spraying plants with pesticides hostathion and monocrotophos, and growing resistant variety Rayada 16-06

and early-maturing variety Padmapani on disease severity.

The late-sown (4 May) crop suffered the lowest disease severity compared with early- and normally sown crops (Table 1). Padmapani completely escaped from the disease. Rayada 16-06 had the lowest disease severity compared with other treatments (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Effect of resistant and early-maturing varieties and pesticide treatments on ufra disease severity in DWR. Assam, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Treatment	Disease severity ^a (% infected tillers/hill)		
Resistant variety (Rayada 16-06)	10.7	(19.6) ^b	b
Early-maturing variety (Padmapani)	0	(4.1)	a
Soaking seeds with hostathion 0.2% for 6 h	38.5	(38.6)	d
Soaking seeds with monocrotophos 0.2% for 6 h	58.5	(50.2)	ef
Spraying with hostathion 0.2% (45 and 80 DAS) ^c	49.0	(44.7)	de
Spraying with monocrotophos 0.2% (45 and 80 DAS)	47.9	(44.1)	de
Soaking seeds + spraying with hostathion 0.2%	13.9	(22.3)	b
Soaking seeds + spraying with monocrotophos 0.2%	25.1	(30.4)	c
Control	65.0	(54.0)	f
LSD (0.05)		6.7	

^aIn a column, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values. ^cDAS = d after sowing.

Table 1. Effect of sowing date on ufra disease severity in DWR. Assam, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Sowing date	Disease severity (% infected tillers/hill)	
20 Mar	91.7	(73.3) ^a
4 Apr	82.0	(64.9)
19 Apr	33.6	(35.4)
4 May	22.0	(8.0)
LSD (0.05)		(4.8)

^aFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values.